

EXCELLENCE IN MECHANICAL DESIGN

BY

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Valcon

○ HALIFAX

○ OSLO ○ STOCKHOLM
○ ODENSE ○ COPENHAGEN
○ LONDON ○ PRAGUE

Established in 2000

VALCON = VALUE CONSULTING

○ SHANGHAI

○ DELHI
○ PUNE
○ BANGALORE ○ CHENNAI

ROBUST DESIGN - THE VALUE IS CLEAR

BUT WHAT ARE THE DESIGN DRIVERS TO ACHIEVE IT?
AND HOW DO WE MEASURE IT IN THE DESIGN DETAIL?

INCREASED **PREDICTABILITY**
IN PRODUCT PERFORMANCE

HIGHER **FIRST PASS YIELD**
AND REDUCED
COMPONENT COSTS

IMPROVED **WORK FLOW** IN
R&D AND PRODUCT
DEVELOPMENT PROCESSES

IMPROVED **INSENSITIVITY** TO
PRODUCTION TOLERANCES
AND AMBIENT CONDITIONS

IN PRODUCTION

A DRIVER IS
REMOVING **WASTE**
(LEAN)

A MEASURE IS THE
AMOUNT OF
DEVIATIONS
(SIGMA)

IN MECHANICAL DESIGN

A DRIVER IS DESIGNING
VARIANTS AND
SELECTING BY
EXPERIENCE

A MEASURE IS
SIMULATE, BUILD AND
TEST THE
PERFORMANCE

ROBUST DESIGN

DRIVEN BY GEOMETRY KINEMATIC INSIGHT
MEASURED BY DESIGN PREDICTABILITY INDEX[®]
IS A WAY TO IMPROVE THE WAY WE WORK

**IN DENMARK WE HAVE A STRONG
TRADITION FOR GEOMETRY
EXCELLENCE**

**JENS OLSENS
WORLD CLOCK**
**ONE OF THE MOST ACURRATE
MECHANICAL CLOCKS IN THE WORLD**

HC ØRSTED SATELLITE
BY FAR THE WORLD'S MOST
ACCURATE SATELLITE FOR
MEASURING MAGNETIC FIELDS

INSULIN DEVICES, WIND TURBINES, PUMPS, HEARING AIDS, THERMOSTATS, CAR STEREO, LEGO AND MANY MORE PRODUCTS

ALL RECOGNISED AS BEST OF THERE KINDS

BASED ON

A STRONG DANISH TRADITION FOR DESIGN

-
GEOMETRY KINEMATIC INSIGHT

-
OUR VISION TO IMPROVE DESIGNS IN THE MARKET BY MAKING THE
ROBUST DESIGN PROCESS LESS ITERATIVE AND LESS EXPERIENCED
BASED

-
AND A STRONG BELIEF THAT THE TIME HAS COME TO CHANGE THE
WAY WE WORK IN DEVELOPMENT

**VALCON DESIGN IS EXCITED TO PARTICIPATE
AND CONTRIBUTE TO ISO RD 2014**